

Intuitive Understanding of Observing Reality: With Extension of the Game Theory

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Abstract

In a context of economics, decision-making takes a high charge in explaining result. By extending the context of the Game Theory to the understanding of P vs NP Problem, fundamental principles of observation can be explained to the very limit of existence.

1 Introduction

Game Theory is about making decisions in rational situations. But in reality, rationality doesn't always count on every situation. In this paper, I will extend the premises of game theory to the use for broader application of observation.

2 Premises of the Game Theory

The premises that form type of the game theory and extending interpretation of them to the change of reality could be presented like this[1][2]:

- Observer(Game player)
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 1) Each observer is a rational being. - In reality, an observer makes consideration to minimize irrational judgment in order to maximize rational judgement.
- Rule of observation(in Game Theory context, An observation corresponds to a game)
 - Timing of each observation(Game playing order)
 - * (Observational Game Theory Premise 2) Determine if it's a concurrent or sequential observation(which corresponds to a game) - In reality, the superiority and inferiority of timing in whether to decide the order of the observation at the same time or sequentially affect the observation.

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- Knowledge and information about an observation (What game players acknowledge through the game)
 - * (Observational Game Theory Premise 3) Perfect recall or not of the observer - In reality, the less knowledge observers have in an observation, the more they fall into error until they make a complete observation.
 - * (Observational Game Theory Premise 4) Whether the observation is made public - In reality, no matter what observation is made, there may be different meanings to each observer.
 - * (Observational Game Theory Premise 5) Whether all the premises for making an observation can be considered - In reality, an observational error throughout recognizing an observation can be created due to grounds that limitations could occur at the time of the observation.
- Strategy
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 6) Action or strategy that an observer can take at every point in time - In reality, observation may prioritize biases rather than most appropriate observation.
- Result factors
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 7) Consequences of the observers' actions - In reality, observers sometimes make wrong observations by mistaking themselves for rational.
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 8) Bias earned by each observer for the realization of the results - In reality, there is always a difference in the distribution of observation when making observations of all observers.

In view of the limitations of game theory, it can be said that observers in the reality have the following characteristics.

1. The observer make considerations to minimize irrational observation in order to maximize rational observation.
2. The observation is influenced by timing, which is whether to make the observation simultaneously or sequentially.
3. The less knowledge observers have in the game, the more mistakes observers will make before making a sound observation.
4. Any observations made may have different results.
5. Different observations could happen due to reasons not taken into account by observations at the time of the observation.
6. The occurrence of observation may prioritize a bias rather than a reality.
7. Observers sometimes mistake themselves for being rational and make the wrong observations.
8. There is always a difference in the distribution of observations when making observations for all observers.

3 Two Types Of Observation And Determinants In A Reality Observation

There are two kinds of game in Game Theory. In corresponding to a strategic game(single observation), Laws of time of observation can be derived in reality:

- (From Observational Game Theory Premise 2) Observation timing affect how observers respond to differences in their detailed observation.
 - (Law of Time 1) Detailed timing reduces distortion of detailed observation among the observers
- (From Observational Game Theory Premise 2) Observation timing affect agreement on details among observers
 - (Law of Time 2) Observations made at the right time led to undisputed agreement on details among the observers

For single observation, it takes an approach for Active Observers AO (those who participated in an observation) like this.

$$\begin{aligned}
 O &= \text{Observer} \\
 TO &= \text{Total Observers} \\
 AO &= \{\text{Observer Group } OG \mid OG \subset \{\text{Observer } O \mid O \in TO\}\} \\
 &= \{OG_1, OG_2, OG_3, \dots, OG_{N(AO)}\}
 \end{aligned}$$

According to the law of energy conservation[3], the energy from any system must always be the same in any unit of observation, so the following formula is derived.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\text{Energy } E = \text{Energy Of a system} \\
 \text{Total Energy Observed } TEO_{AO,E} & \\
 &= \text{Total Energy Observed by Active Observers } AO \\
 \text{Partial Observation } PO_{OG,E} & \\
 &= \text{Partial Observation of Observation Group } OG \\
 \text{Partial Observation Distribution } POD_{OG,AO} &= \frac{PO_{OG,E}}{TEO_{AO,E}} \\
 \exists E, \exists AO \Rightarrow TEO_{AO,E} &= \sum_n^{N(AO)} TEO_{AE,E} \cdot POD_{OG_n,AO} \\
 (0 \leq POD_{OG_n,AO} \leq 1) &
 \end{aligned}$$

Law of Time 1, 2 means that an observation differs in time and active observers want to make observation in time when their details from an observation get maximized.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Optimized } t_{AO,wanted}^* &= \text{Desired period of an observation for AO} \\
&= \arg \max_t TEO(AO, E, t)
\end{aligned}$$

Extensive-form game is a game about successive time in one system. It corresponds with repeated observations about the same space of a system. The factors that can be adjusted during the observation space are:

- (From Observational Game Theory Premise 8) Observations considering space affect the details of the whole and the parts
 - (Law of Space 1) Each observer tries to maximize the details of observation of a reality.
- (From Observational Game Theory Premise 8) Observations considering space affect styles of the observers considering the whole and the parts
 - (Law of Space 2) The considerations for the parts aim for the detail itself, and the considerations for the whole prefer to complete the details.

Field is a place where energies are placed in. And observations happen in a field where total details of partial observations' in specific period gets maximized.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Field } F &= \{E | E \text{ is an energy}\} \\
\forall (\text{Energy } E) &\in \arg \max_F \sum_{N(\{AO|\forall AO\})} TEO_{AO,E}
\end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, the factors that can be adjusted during the observation progress environment are as follows.

- Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 1 - An observation may interfere with the other observations resulting in distortion of the detailed distribution of the observations.
- Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 2 - An observation may distort the total observations' distribution resulting in interfere to the detailed distribution of the observations.
- Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 1 - An observation may clarify the total observations' distribution resulting in overcoming the biases of the detailed distribution of the observations.
- Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 2 - An observation may overcome the biases of the total observations' distribution resulting in clarifying the biases of the detailed distribution of the observations.

By Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 1, Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 1, A field where energies are placed in can relate to detailed distribution $POD_{AO,OG}$. And by Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 1, A field where energies are placed in can affect total energy observed $TEO_{AO,E}$.

By Law of Time 1 + Law of Space 2, Law of Time 2 + Law of Space 2, A detailed energy distribution is related to total energy observed. And by the preceding subject, it is a structure of the larger field that forms relation between the detailed energy distribution and total energy observed. We will assume this distribution observed from the larger field as a mapping function Larger Field Observed LFO at period t applies to the relation of detailed distribution $POD_{AO,OG}$ and total energy observed $TEO_{AO,E}$.

Larger Field Observed is made up with set of rules R . Rules are for sustaining a field itself.

$$R = \{r \mid r \text{ is a rule set in } \exists F\}$$

$$(0 \leq LFO_t(\exists F, R) \leq 1)$$

According to the preceding premise, through the premise of Game Theory, I will classify them as follows:

- Fallacy of perception
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 3) The less knowledge observer have in an observation, the more errors observer would make until observer makes a perfect observation.
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 7) Observers sometimes make the wrong observations by mistakenly thinking observers themselves are rational.
- Fallacy of memory
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 4) Any observation made may have different results.
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 5) Different observations could happen due to reasons not taken into account by observations at the time of the observation.
- Fallacy of opportunity
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 1) The observer make considerations to minimize irrational observation in order to maximize rational observation.
 - (Observational Game Theory Premise 6) The occurrence of observation may prioritize a bias rather than a reality.

The perception, memory and opportunity fallacy of observers meet distortions in time and space. In reality, it's about observation of energy that could be placed in. According to Rule 7, 5 and 1, these fallacies make observation to be placed in errors of Total Energy Observed $TEO_{AO,E,t}$. On the other hand, according to Rule 3, 4 and 6, these fallacies' effectiveness changes over time.

Rule 7 is about the Active Observers AO . Rule 5 is about an energy E . Rule 1 is about an observation group OG , and by that TEO and POD is affected.

Firstly, observation group relation between TEO and POD is affected by probability of being fall into fallacy of opportunity. So, what is fallacy of opportunity? it is a probability of

getting more bias than what Active Observers expected. I will assume that E_{oe} is an energy with opportunity fallacy.

Opportunity fallacy probability function $OE(E) =$

$$Pr(\{E_{oe} \mid E_{oe} \text{ is an energy when } \frac{\text{observed } PO_{OG,E}}{\text{observed } TEO_{AO,E}} > \text{expected } POD_{AO,OG}\} \mid \forall E)$$

Secondly, energy is affected by the other interactions. So, what is fallacy of memory? it is a probability to synchronize to what is expected which is less than what should be real. I will assume that E_{me} is an energy with opportunity fallacy.

Memory fallacy probability function $ME(E) =$

$$Pr(\{E_{me} \mid E_{me} \text{ is an energy when } \frac{\text{observed } PO_{OG,E}}{\text{observed } TEO_{AO,E}} < \text{expected } POD_{AO,OG}\} \mid \forall E)$$

Thirdly, energy is affected by the observation of the observers' detailed observation of distribution. Fallacy of perception is a probability to distort the detailed distribution by observers' arbitrary perception. I will assume that E_{pe} is an energy with perception fallacy.

Perception fallacy probability function $PE(E) =$

$$Pr(\{E_{pe} \mid E_{pe} \text{ is an energy when } \frac{\text{expected } PO_{OG,E}}{\text{expected } TEO_{AO,E}} \neq (\text{observed } POD_{AO,OG})\} \mid \forall E)$$

So, Total Energy Observed with the considerations of discussions above can be in form like this:

$$TEO_{AO,E} = \sum_n^{N(AO)} LFO(AO, OG_n, F) \cdot TEO_{AO,E} \cdot POD_{AO,OG_n} \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E))$$

4 Concealment of Reality with Searching for Reality

In reality, the observation is given every time, and the observation target is constantly exposed to the observation itself. But observer's perception usually has limitation. Therefore, concealment of reality happens with the innate limitation of observer's observations. Through this, an error term is created throughout the timeline and makes symmetry with an effort of searching for reality physically.

For this, the two principles can be derived from this:

1. Every observation makes an effort of searching for clear perception of reality.
2. But with the innate limitation (or with the symmetric perception offset from a timeline), an error term is created and it overlaps throughout timeline.

Intuitively, cost for correcting the perception throughout time gets relatively high as it stays in an error of perception. So in economic sense, observers innately seek symmetry throughout time essentially to protect observer's perception from forever being in an error prior to the perception before.

So, it can be summarized into these terms:

- Searching for Reality: Wrong perception of reality likely to be corrected as time goes by.
- Concealment of Reality: Cost of correcting wrong perception gets relatively high as time goes by.

In other words, searching for reality is needed to reduce the waste of costs while minimizing concealment of reality.

According to the upper discussion, concealment of reality is an error(CR_t) that has a limit bound for an energy that can be perceived in period t with symmetry with the next repeated observation. On the other hand, searching for reality can be a symmetry(SR_t) that has a limit bound for an energy that can be perceived in period t with maximizing the reality of the current observation. That makes gap between the actual observation from the currently expected energy.

$$\begin{aligned}
TEO_{AO,E} &= \sum_n^{N(AO)} LFO(AO, OG_n, F) \cdot TEO_{AO,E} \cdot POD_{AO,OG_n} \\
&\quad \cdot (1 - OE(E))(1 - ME(E))(1 - PE(E)) \\
Optimal\ t_{wanted}^* &= \arg \max_t TEO_{AO,E} \\
Optimal\ t_{actual}^* &= \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \\
&\quad (CR_t \geq 0, SR_t \geq 0) \\
\exists E &\Leftrightarrow Optimal\ t_{actual}^* = \arg \max_t (TEO_{AO,E} - CR_t + SR_t) \approx 0
\end{aligned}$$

5 Extension from the P vs NP Problem's Conclusion

Observation takes count as a form of countable event. Many observations means multiple countable events set from single observation. Assuming that there is a countable infinite set of observation set as \aleph_0 . And if every observation is to be decided happen or not within specific period, it takes a combination form like this:

$$2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_1$$

And by extending it through the Continuum Hypothesis[4], it corresponds every moment of infinity to be a specific period to decide every observation to happen or not.

$$2^{\aleph_n} = \aleph_{n+1}$$

And it can be extended to the understanding of the P vs NP Problem[5] like this:

1. Every moment of an observation contains a possibility of creating the next moment of observation.
2. It's undecidable to limit a possibility of the next moment of observation.
3. An observation is an event that forms a minimum unit of reality.

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